

Using InSAR Time Series Analysis to Characterize Tunnel Induced Surface Deformation

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As transportation corridors reach capacity, tunneling has become an increasingly necessary means of providing infrastructure to densely populated urban areas. Tunnels are often constructed close to the surface, increasing the likelihood of excavation induced ground subsidence and the potential impact on overlying established core infrastructure such as buildings, bridges, and utility lines. It is therefore necessary to quantify surface deformation induced by tunneling processes in order to better understand the factors that contribute to surface subsidence. Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) is an ideal tool for measuring surface deformation related to tunnel construction because of its ability to make measurements with sub-centimeter accuracy over large areas, as well as the availability of historical data needed to identify any pre-construction deformation. Theoretical analysis of tunneling in homogeneous media indicates that surface settlement profiles are transversely Gaussian in shape, with maximum displacement observed directly above the center of an individual tunnel. However, surface settlement geometry is dependent upon a variety of factors including geology, water table depth, and excavation method. Here we apply Persistent Scatterer (PS) and Small Baselines Subset (SBAS) InSAR time-series techniques incorporating ascending and descending Sentinel-1 data acquired during recently completed and ongoing tunneling projects in the United States. Surface deformation measured before, during, and after tunnel excavation allows us to make inferences about subsurface conditions and better characterize the impact of tunnel excavation on overlying ground and structural deformation.